

The Impact of Service Quality on Customers Satisfaction and Loyalty: A Case Study of Commercial Banks in Battambang City, Cambodia

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Abstract

This research aims to understand banks' customers' demographic information and investigate the effects of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in Battambang city, Battambang Province, Cambodia. Researchers used a quantitative approach to survey 289 customers using various bank services and employed descriptive statistics and multiple regression to analyze the data. The data analysis revealed that tangibles, assurance, reliability, and empathy have positive effects on customer satisfaction and loyalty. However, empathy does not positively affect customer satisfaction and loyalty. In addition, hypothesis testing supported hypotheses H1a, H1b, H2a, H2b, H4a, H4b, H5a, H5b, H6a and H6b. Researchers provide some recommendations to banks for their quality services to retain customers.

Keywords: *tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, satisfaction, loyalty.*

JEL Classification codes: *G21*

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Introduction

Cambodia is experiencing growth across various sectors, with rapid expansion in the service industry due to rising consumer demand. In 2023, economic growth is projected at 6.1%. The banking and financial sector, overseen by the National Bank of Cambodia, has also seen robust growth, with significant increases in assets, credit, deposits, and service locations, including 51 commercial banks, 14 specialized banks, and numerous microfinance institutions. Efforts to enhance central banking services are ongoing, but there is a need for improved digital security. Additionally, the World Bank's 2018 Human Capital Index report revealed that Cambodia's human capital index score was 0.49.

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Service Quality

According to Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1985), service quality is defined through the gap model, which highlights the difference between customer expectations and their perceptions of actual service performance. This definition underscores the SERVQUAL model, which identifies five key dimensions of service quality: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. In contrast, Cronin and Taylor's (1992) SERVPERF model emphasizes performance alone, asserting that service quality is best assessed through customers' perceptions of service performance, excluding the expectations component. Gronroos (1984) proposed a two-dimensional model of service quality, distinguishing between technical quality (what is delivered) and functional quality (how it is delivered) and considering the company's image, which influences customers' perceptions of quality.

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction refers to the fulfillment or pleasure derived from meeting an individual's desires, expectations, or needs, resulting in feelings of contentment and joy (Smith & Johnson, 2020). Kotler et al. (2012) define customer satisfaction as the extent to which a product or service meets or exceeds customer expectations (Chork et al., 2024; Tieng et al., 2024 a). The generation of customer satisfaction is crucial for business success. To increase customer satisfaction, it is important to focus on the factors that affect customer perceptions. Satisfied customers are more likely to make repeat purchases and recommend a company's products or services to others. Customers are central to any business. Therefore, for a business to succeed, it must prioritize satisfying its customers. Companies that focus on increasing customer satisfaction may see more referrals from existing customers, greater customer loyalty, and higher profits. If customer expectations are not met, dissatisfaction will occur. Hence, companies must emphasize service quality, product quality, and value for money, as these factors significantly impact customer satisfaction (Ooko, Aila & Odondo, 2023; Tieng et al., 2024 b).

Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty is characterized by a strong and unwavering commitment or allegiance to an individual, group, cause, or organization, often demonstrated through consistent support, trust, and sacrifice (Smith, E.E., 2015). Fida et al. (2020) highlight that service quality and brand significantly impact customer loyalty in the Pakistani banking sector. Customer loyalty refers to the tendency of customers to repeatedly patronize a business on the basis of their past experiences and future expectations (Arslan, 2020; Tieng et al., 2024 c).

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical model guiding this research is illustrated in the figure below, adapted from Agus et al. (2007) and Caruana (2002). This research investigates five factors of service quality, namely, tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, as adapted from Agus et al. (2007). Agus's study examined service quality within Malaysia's public sector, focusing on both management and customer perceptions.

Figure 1. Research Model
Source: Kheng et al., 2010

Overview of the Service Quality Model

The SERVQUAL model is a widely recognized multidimensional tool considered one of the most effective for measuring service quality. In accordance with Presbury (2009), this model examines customers' perceptions and expectations of the services provided, identifying key factors that significantly impact service outcomes. To achieve high levels of customer satisfaction, service providers must bridge the gap between customer expectations and the actual service delivered.

SERVQUAL is extensively used to measure service quality and customer satisfaction within the service industry (Roslan et al., 2015; Gencer & Akkucuk, 2017). It is praised for its reliability, validity, and broad applicability across various service institutions and is often used more widely than other models (Munusamy et al., 2010; Gencer & Akkucuk, 2017). Pizam et al. (2016) noted that SERVQUAL is also commonly applied in studies within the hospitality and tourism sectors. However, the model has faced criticism for its general applicability across all service industries, especially when service delivery is heavily dependent on the provider and context. Gencer and Akkucuk (2017) reported that SERVPERF, which focuses solely on performance elements without incorporating expectations as SERVQUAL does, is the second most commonly used model. Although SERVPERF is noted for requiring less time to administer due to fewer questions, it has been criticized for its inconsistencies. Despite these criticisms, some argue against using SERVQUAL to measure service quality, suggesting that quality is often defined by users (Roslan et al., 2015). Research by Shafiq et al. (2019) has identified five dimensions of SERVQUAL, which are detailed below.

Tangibles: Presbury (2009) and Giannakos et al. (2012) describe tangibles as the physical aspects of the service, including the condition of facilities, equipment, personnel, and materials used to interact with customers. In the banking context, tangibles encompass the bank's equipment, furnishings, and staff.

2. Reliability: Reliability, as described by Presbury (2009) and Giannakos et al. (2012), refers to the ability to deliver promised services dependably and accurately. For banks, meeting promised timelines is crucial; failure to do so can negatively affect customer perceptions and adversely impact

the bank. Aleshaiwy (2015) highlighted that reliability is a significant factor in customer satisfaction and a competitive advantage.

3. Responsiveness: According to Presbury (2009) and Giannakos et al. (2012), responsiveness involves the willingness of service providers to assist customers promptly and effectively. In banking, this pertains to the bank staff's ability to address customer needs and respond to requests in a timely manner (Aleshaiwy, 2015).

4. Assurance: Assurance, as defined by Presbury (2009) and Giannakos et al. (2012), relates to the knowledge and courtesy of service providers and their ability to instill trust and confidence. In banking, this dimension reflects the bank's ability to convey reliability and competence during customer interactions.

5. Empathy: Empathy, according to Presbury (2009) and Giannakos et al. (2012), involves understanding and addressing individual customer needs with care. In the banking sector, this means engaging deeply with customers to understand their needs and provide exceptional care. Aleshaiwy (2015) noted that despite many banks offering additional facilities, poor behavior by bank staff often leads to customer dissatisfaction.

Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction and service quality are intricately linked, with high service quality generally leading to high customer satisfaction. However, the banking sector often lacks a universally recognized standard for measuring service quality. Therefore, competing by maintaining high service quality is a vital strategy (Felix, 2017). Lasser et al., as cited by Suda S. and Sarunya L. (2001), investigated the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in the private banking sector via two prominent measures: SERVQUAL and the technical or functional quality approach. They compared SERVQUAL with the technical or functional quality model, assessing the various dimensions of each service quality model and their effects on customer satisfaction. They reported that customer satisfaction is a multidimensional construct, with different dimensions of service quality affecting satisfaction in diverse ways (Felix, 2017).

Service Quality and Customer Loyalty

Kotler and Keller (2015) define service quality as the overall characteristic of a product or service in fulfilling customer needs. Service quality plays a crucial role in creating value for both customers and companies by providing high-quality experiences, which in turn enhances long-term profitability. For service companies, the quality of the service delivery process is essential, as it directly influences the quality of outcomes experienced by customers. Research by Janahi and Almubarak (2017) demonstrates that service quality significantly affects customer satisfaction. These findings are consistent with Ashraf's (2014) research, which also highlights the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction. Furthermore, Fauzi and Suryani (2018) identify service quality as a major factor driving customer satisfaction among users of banking services in Indonesia. Shanka (2015) emphasized that the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction is critical for fostering customer loyalty to banks (Rusmahafi & Wulandari, 2020).

Materials and Methods

Research Design

For this study, the researchers used a quantitative research design to investigate the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty. To determine the sample size for the survey, the researchers employed a random sampling method. Yamane Taro (1967) was used to determine the appropriate sample size.

Participants

A total of 398 customers using banking services in Battambang city were selected for the study.

Instruments and Procedure

There were 43 items of questionnaires applied in this research study. Primary data were collected via questionnaires aligned with the research objectives, which targeted customers using banking services in Battambang city. Research materials for this study were sourced from the library of the National University of Battambang, research reports, books, and other materials, including internet resources, libraries, e-books, and relevant news articles.

Data Analysis

The data from the bank customer survey will be analyzed via quantitative methods. The data will be input into SPSS version 26 and examined through various models, including regression analysis, multiple regression, Cronbach's alpha reliability, and statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation.

Results

Table 1. Results for the Tangible Variable

Items	Tangible	Level of Agreement (%)				M	SD
		1	2	3	4		
TA1	The bank is well-equipped.	.5	2.3	76.1	21.1	3.18	.472
TA2	The physical layout of equipment and furniture is comfortable for customers interacting with staff.	.8	4.5	74.4	20.4	3.14	.509
TA3	Bank employees are well-dressed and appear neat.	.0	1.5	60.1	38.4	3.37	.514
TA4	The appearance of the physical facilities of the Bank matches the type of services offered.	.5	3.8	72.4	23.4	3.19	.507
TA5	Physical environment of the bank is clean.	.5	3.8	61.6	34.2	3.29	.560
	Total					3.23	.512

According to Table 1, the tangible variables have average scores and standard deviations ranging from (M = 3.14 to M = 3.37 and SD = .509 to SD = .514). Most customers who use banking services in Battambang have a high level of agreement with one statement: "Bank employees are well dressed and appear neat." with (M = 3.37 and SD = .514). In particular, customers who use banking services have a low level of agreement with the following statement: "The physical layout of equipment and furniture is comfortable for customers interacting with staff" (M = 3.14 and SD = .509). Therefore, the lowest average score of customer perception indicates disagreement or dissatisfaction, which requires the banking institution to improve on this point and equip furniture to be more comfortable.

Table 2. Results for the Reliability Variable

Items	Reliability	Level of Agreement (%)				M	SD
		1	2	3	4		
RL1	The bank provides prompt services customer.	.5	3.5	66.1	29.6	3.25	.541
RL2	Bank provides its services at the time it promises to do so.	.3	8.8	73.1	17.8	3.09	.519
RL3	The bank keeps its records accurately.	.5	1.5	65.8	32.2	3.30	.519
RL4	Services and charges are reliable.	.8	4.8	69.3	25.1	3.19	.543
RL5	The bank performs service right the first time	.8	11.1	65.1	23.1	3.11	.601
	Total					3.19	.545

According to Table 2, the reliability variables have average scores and standard deviations ranging from $M = 3.09$ to $M = 3.30$ and $SD = .519$ to $SD = .519$. Most customers who use banking services in Battambang city have a high level of agreement with the statement "Banks keep their records accurate" ($M = 3.30$ and $SD = .519$). In contrast, our customers have a low level of agreement regarding the stated statement: "Bank provides on-demand services" ($M = 3.09$ and $SD = .519$). As such, the lowest average score of consumer perceptions indicates disagreement, which requires the banking institution to improve on this point and try to deliver more services as promised.

Table 3. Results for the Responsiveness Variable

Items	Responsiveness	Level of Agreement (%)				M	SD
		1	2	3	4		
RN1	The bank provides prompt services customer.	1.0	12.8	63.1	23.1	3.08	.627
RN2	Employees of bank are always willing to help customers.	.3	11.8	68.1	19.8	3.08	.567
RN3	Bank arranges special care for special customers.	1.0	15.3	63.3	20.4	3.03	.630
RN4	Employees of bank reply to any query from customers.	.8	6.8	63.8	28.6	3.20	.586
RN5	The bank makes information easily obtained by customers.	3.3	69.6	27.1	.00	3.24	.498
	Total					3.13	.582

According to Table 3, the response variables have a mean score and standard deviation ranging from $M = 3.03$ to $M = 3.24$ and $SD = .498$ to $SD = .630$. Most customers who use banking services in Battambang City have a high level of agreement with the following statement: "Banks provide easy information to customers" ($M = 3.24$ and $SD = .498$). In contrast, our clients have a low level of agreement regarding the stated statement: "The Bank provides special care for special clients" ($M = 3.03$ and $SD = .630$). Accordingly, the lowest average point of view of customers indicates disagreement, which requires the banking institution to improve on this point and should provide special care for special customers to further strengthen services.

Table 4. Results for the Empathy Variable

Items	Empathy	Level of Agreement (%)				M	SD
		1	2	3	4		
EM1	Customers have faith in the services provided by the bank.	.3	6.5	79.6	13.6	3.07	.455
EM2	Employees of bank give personal attention to the customers.	.3	13.8	66.6	19.3	3.05	.583
EM3	Employees of bank know the needs attention of the customers.	.8	11.3	71.9	16.1	3.03	.551
EM4	The operating hours of the bank are convenient for all their.	.3	8.8	66.6	24.4	3.15	.565
EM5	Employees of the bank give customers personal service.	4.0	29.9	52.5	13.6	2.46	.733
	Total					3.01	.577

According to Table 4, the empathy variables have average scores and standard deviations ranging from $M = 2.76$ to $M = 3.15$ and $SD = .455$ to $SD = .733$. Most customers who use banking services in Battambang city have a high level of agreement with the following statement: "The bank has a reasonable operating hour for all customers", which has ($M = 3.15$ and $SD = .565$). In contrast,

our customers have a low level of agreement with the statement "The bank staff provides personalized service to customers" available ($M = 2.76$ and $SD = .733$). Accordingly, the lowest average score of customer perception indicates disagreement, which requires the banking institution to improve on this point. Bank staff should provide additional personal services to customers to further strengthen the service.

Table 5. Results for the Assurance Variable

Items	Assurance	Level of Agreement (%)				M	SD
		1	2	3	4		
AS1	When customers have problems, the Bank is sympathetic and reassuring.	4.8	41.7	44.7	8.8	2.58	.719
AS2	Customers are safe to deal with the services of the Bank.	.8	5.8	74.6	18.8	3.12	.514
AS3	Clients can trust the employees of the bank.	.3	9.0	72.1	18.6	3.09	.528
AS4	Employees of the bank are polite to customers.	.5	6.0	63.1	30.4	3.23	.575
AS5	When customers have problems, the Bank is sympathetic and reassuring.	4.3	.0	70.4	25.4	3.21	.503
	Total					3.05	.568

According to Table 5, the assurance variables have average scores and standard deviations ranging from ($M = 2.58$ to $M = 3.23$ and $SD = .503$ to $SD = .719$). Most customers who use banking services in Battambang have a high level of agreement with the following statement: "Employees of the bank are polite to customers." with ($M = 3.23$ and $SD = .575$). In contrast, our customers have a low level of agreement on a statement: "When customers have problems, the Bank is sympathetic and reassuring" ($M = 2.58$ and $SD = .719$). Thus, the lowest average score of customer perception indicates disagreement, which requires the banking institution to be understanding in any particular case when the customer encounters a problem.

Table 6. Results for the Satisfaction Variable

Items	Satisfaction	Level of Agreement (%)				M	SD
		1	2	3	4		
S1	I am satisfied with the overall service quality offered by the bank.	.8	8.5	73.4	17.4	3.07	.533
S2	I am satisfied with the professional competence of bank.	.3	6.0	77.4	16.3	3.10	.474
S3	I am satisfied with the performance of the frontline employees of the bank.	.3	6.5	74.4	18.8	3.12	.501
S4	I am comfortable with the relationship with bank.	.3	10.8	67.3	21.6	3.10	.570
S5	I intend to continue using mobile services from the bank for a long time.	.8	6.5	60.3	32.4	3.24	.601
	Total					3.12	.526

According to Table 6, the satisfaction variables have average scores and standard deviations ranging from $M = 3.07$ to $M = 3.24$ and $SD = .570$ to $SD = .601$. Most customers who use banking services in Battambang City have a high level of agreement with the following statement: "I intend to continue using mobile services from the bank for a long time." with ($M = 3.24$ and $SD = .601$). In contrast, our customers have a low level of agreement regarding the stated statement: "I am satisfied with the overall service quality offered by the bank." with ($M = 3.07$ and $SD = .533$). Thus,

the lowest average score of consumer perceptions indicates disagreement, which requires the banking institution to improve on this point and try to provide better services.

Table 7. Results for the Loyalty Variable

Items	Loyalty	Level of Agreement (%)				M	SD
		1	2	3	4		
L1	Even if another operator's price is lower than others, I will.	3.3	23.9	59.8	13.1	2.83	.686
L2	I will encourage friends and relatives to use the services offered.	.5	10.6	73.6	15.3	3.04	.527
L3	I am willing to say positive things about bank to other people.	1.8	17.3	66.6	14.3	2.93	.619
L4	The bank is capable of providing the best service.	.3	5.5	72.4	21.9	3.16	.509
L5	I am unlikely to switch to other banks soon.	2.3	12.6	65.7	19.4	3.02	.641
	Total					3.00	.596

According to Table 7, the Loyalty variables have average scores and standard deviations ranging from (M = 2.83 to M = 3.16 and SD = .509 to SD = .686). Most customers who use banking services in Battambang City have a high level of agreement with the following statement: "The bank is capable of providing the best service." with (M = 3.16 and SD = .509). In contrast, our customers have the lowest level of agreement with the statement: "Even if another operator's price is the lowest than others, I will." with (M = 2.83 and SD = .686). Therefore, the lowest average point of consumer sentiment indicates disagreement, which requires the banking institution to improve on this point and try to lower operating costs.

The Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty

Testing hypotheses that affect variables, satisfaction, and loyalty

Table 8. Summary of Path Coefficients and Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Relationship	Beta	SE	T Value	Sig.	Decision
H1a	TA→S	.120	.52	2.448	.015**	Supported
H1b	TA→L	.132	.061	2.492	.003***	Supported
H2a	RL→S	.155	.058	2.680	.008***	Supported
H2b	RL→L	.67	.068	2.674	.013**	Supported
H3a	RN→S	.127	.056	.449	.654	Rejected
H3b	RN→L	-.073	.066	-1.118	.264	Rejected
H4a	AS→S	.262	.051	5.085	.000***	Supported
H4b	AS→L	.153	.060	2.741	.006***	Supported
H5a	EM→S	.276	.048	5.271	.000***	Supported
H5b	EM→L	.376	.045	6.653	.000***	Supported
H6a	L→S+SQ	.372	.034	7.458	.000***	Supported
H6b	S→L	.649	.042	16.946	.000***	Supported

Note: Beta = regression weight. SE = standard error. ***P < .05, T > 1.98

Testing that honesty interacts with satisfaction with service quality

To study the relationships among those variables, the researchers used the 26th generation SPSS program, following a formula (Analyze => Regression => Linear), to predict the value of a variable on the basis of the values of two or more other variables (Laerd, n.d.).

Table 9. Results of Multiple Regression

	Step 1	Step 2	Step 1 and Step 2
Dependent variables	Loyalty	Satisfaction	Loyalty
Independent variables	Standardized coefficients-β		
Tangible	0.132	0.120	0.081
Reliability	0.167	0.155	0.099
Responsiveness	-0.073	0.027	-0.08
Assurance	0.153	0.262	0.04
Empathy	0.376	0.276	0.256
Satisfaction			0.426
Steps summary	Step 1	Step 2	Step 1 and Step 2
R2	0.391	0.475	0.486
Adjusted R2	0.383	0.468	0.479
Durbin Watson	2.024	2.036	2.039
F value	50.267	70.841	61.577

Discussion

According to the forecast analysis in Table 8, the tangible assets with the score ($B = .120$, $T = 2.448$, $P = .015$) were also found to be important for customer satisfaction. The bank's customers consider monetary assets important to them. Tangible assets ($B = .132$, $T = 2.492$, $P = .013$) also have a strong influence on customer loyalty. This result is consistent with the findings of Surehanded et al. (2003).

According to Table 8, reliability was found to be important for customer satisfaction with a score ($B = .155$, $T = 2,680$, $P = .008$). Reliability was also found to be positively correlated with customer loyalty with a score ($B = .167$, $T = 2.674$, $P = .008$). This finding is supported by previous researchers, including Nguyen & Leblanc (2001) and Bellini et al. (2005). The findings in Table 4.12 show that the results of this hypothesis test also indicate that the responses found to have a score ($B = .027$, $T = .449$, $P = .654$) are irrelevant. Positive with no customer satisfaction. The relationship between customer response and loyalty was also unsupported, with scores of $B = -.073$, $T = -1.118$, $P = .264$. This result contrasts with those of other studies (Jun & Cai, 2001; Diaz & Ruiz, 2002; Joseph et al., 2005; Glaveli et al., 2006). Customer loyalty is an important factor that a bank must ensure to be profitable. The more educated and educated customers are, the more their needs increase. To maintain stability in their business, banks need to improve their customer service campaigns. With the advent of foreign banks, local banks need to improve the quality of their services by sending more experienced staff to serve customers.

According to Ndubisi (2006), the provision of personal, flexible and customized services can satisfy customers. This finding is consistent with the findings of this study that empathy had a positive effect on customer satisfaction, as shown by the scores ($B = .276$, $T = 5,271$, $P = .000$) in Table 8. Sympathetic scores ($B = .376$, $T = 6,653$, $P = .000$) also have a significant positive relationship with customer loyalty. This evidence is supported by the findings of Butcher (2001), Ndubisi (2006) and Ehigie (2006). As mentioned by Butcher (2001), customer-service friendships have a significant effect on increasing customer loyalty.

Guarantees are found to be an important predictor of customer satisfaction with a score ($B = .262$, $T = 5.085$, $P = .000$), in accordance with Ndubisi (2006), who noted that clear communication is a strong indicator of overall satisfaction and an important source of customer satisfaction in the Malaysian banking sector. This study also shows the important relationship between assurance and customer loyalty in Table 8, with a score of $B = .153$, $T = 2.741$, $P = .006$, which is consistent with previous studies by Lympelopoulous et al. (2006) and Ndubisi (2006).

Table 8 also shows that loyalty has a mediating effect on the relationship between the dimensional quality of service (tangible, reliable, responsive, compassionate and guaranteed) and customer satisfaction ($B = .372$, $T = 7.458$, $P = .000$). This is consistent with studies conducted by Caruana (2002), Butcher (2001), Ehigie (2006) and Lam & Burton (2006).

The results of the analysis in Table 8 also show that the satisfaction variable has a positive effect, with a score ($B = .649$, $T = 16.946$, $P = .000$) of the significance level leading to an acceptable H6a hypothesis. Regression was performed as proposed by Baron & Kenny (1996), performing a separate four-step analysis process:

Step 1: Customer loyalty as an independent variable and the dimension of service quality as an independent variable

Step 2: Customer satisfaction as a nondependent variable and the dimension of service quality as Independent variable

Steps 3 & 4: Customer loyalty is a nondependent variable, and customer satisfaction, along with the dimension of service quality, are independent variables.

According to Table 9, responsiveness (IV) was found to be negatively related to customer satisfaction and loyalty (DV). Thus, no interaction occurs. In particular, other service quality variables, such as material wealth, trust, assurance and compassion, were found to support customer satisfaction and loyalty. Thus, an interaction occurs.

Conclusion

This research concludes that users' perceptions of four out of the five variables—tangibility, assurance, reliability, and empathy—are positive, which contributes to higher service quality. When banks provide high-quality services, it leads to increased customer satisfaction and loyalty, driving the bank's growth and stability. However, the fifth variable, responsiveness, received negative feedback from users due to slow responses and failure to meet customer needs, which adversely affects customer satisfaction and loyalty.

To address this issue, banks must increase their staff's responsiveness to exceed customer expectations. Bank managers should prioritize the hiring of qualified staff and implement effective training programs to ensure professional and customer-focused service. The research findings further indicate that service quality has a positive effect on customer satisfaction and loyalty, reaffirming that bank customers in Battambang city are generally satisfied and loyal to the banks they use.

In summary, studying service quality is vital for strengthening financial institutions, helping them better engage with their customers and fostering satisfaction and loyalty. These factors are key drivers of institutional growth and competitiveness in the banking sector.

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Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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